

Research Through Games: Collaboration of Sister Projects

GREAT + EPIC-WE

This document describes our exploratory collaboration intent between sister projects GREAT (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation) (Hollins, 2024; GREAT, 2025) and EPIC-WE (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments) (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024a; EPIC-WE, 2025).

Introduction

The GREAT project employs games and playful methods to foster dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders. These interactive formats enable the public to express their perspectives on policy, contributing to its development. EPIC-WE is a related initiative that supports young people to engage with and shape European culture by designing and sharing cultural values and heritage through game-making. In both projects, games and the process of creating them serve as tools for engagement, encouraging reflection, discussion, and expression of complex societal concepts such as values and fairness. This shared approach provides a foundation for collaboration between the two initiatives.

This document describes our initial collaborative effort between GREAT and EPIC-WE to share developed methodologies that create further insights for both projects. Through the EPIC-WE project, a game jam method has been developed to engage participants with themes that reflect cultural heritage and European values. This method structures game-making into four phases: experience, play, imagine, and create (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024b). The GREAT project has developed methods for qualitative playful discussions and quantitative surveys through gaming communities to elicit public views and attitudes to important policy and climate conversations. The playful discussion activities (scenario discussions, reflective prompts) could serve as the thematic foundation for an EPIC-WE game jam if used in the “experience” phase. Subsequently, through the “play” and “imagine” phases of the game jam participants collaborate to transform these reflections into a playable game. The time spent in the game making process may deepen participant reflection upon the discussion activities, fostering shared sensemaking, with an expression of the developed views through creative game design.

The theme of the experience phase for this exploratory work will be Water Security. We will use playful discussion activities created in the GREAT case study GCS2 (Watson, 2025). Through making games based on this interaction, we will explore:

- 1) How the game making process helps develop ideas, values, and sensemaking of water security issues after these issues have been discussed.

- 2) Participants reflections on what it is like to take part in a game jam
- 3) Participant perceptions of their skillset development by taking part in a game jam
- 4) Reflect upon the implementation of the EPIC-WE game jam method to inform its adaptability across use cases.

Method

EPIC-WE Game Jam Overview

An overview of the EPIC-WE game jam methodology can be seen in figure 1. Each phase captures a stage in the game design process. Highlighting the aim, expected processes, outcomes, and the tools used to transition groups between design stages.

Phase	Experience	Play	Imagine	Create
Aims	Experience games, culture, and values	Play with concepts of games, culture, and values	Imagine games, culture, and values	Create games, culture, and values
Process	Introduce/Evoke, Team-up, Define/Decide	Brainstorm, tinker, conceptualise ideas	Iterate, prototype towards a finalised idea	Iterate, refine game / culture. Document + present work
Outcome	Game / Culture elements	Game + Culture concepts + Mock-Ups	Playbale Prototype, Concept Art	Game for culture
Transition Tool	Ideation Cubes, Wheel	Hub Council	Playtest Game	Game for culture / Expo

Figure 1. Overview of the EPIC-WE game jam methodology adapted from Nørgård & Holflod (2024b). The four phases describe the expected design process. The aims highlight goals of each stage while the process and outcome describe expected tasks and artefacts created at each stage. The transition tools bring groups through to the next phase of the design process.

The four phases are as follows.

Experience: Participants experience games to understand their structure and configuration. Cultural and value-based themes of the game jam are explored actively. For example, through heritage exhibitions, stories, and environmental exploration. In this stage game jam groups are formed and general reflections and discussions on games and the theme are engaged with. This sets out the broad theme and game structure directions that the groups want to follow.

Play: Once teams and direction are established, they can play with ideas and thoughts upon the given theme and game design. Participants are encouraged to be free with ideas at this stage and engage with perspective sharing to build initial ideas. These ideas are roughly prototyped and given feedback by game and discipline experts to help refine ideas, point out potential issues, and encourage groups.

Imagine: By this phase, the groups will have chosen a direction and have developed a game to play test. Through playtesting, feedback, and iteration, the game design shows significant refinement.

Create: The chosen idea is ready for game jam production. With the aim of presenting the game at an exhibition or online, this is a chance for the game jam groups refine their idea towards a prototype that can be used by the public.

Participants

For this exploratory work, we will be using students within the University of Greater Manchester at undergraduate and post graduate educational levels.

Method Adaptations

While the game jam offers a great chance for participants to explore important topics, it's also important to consider their time, energy, and other commitments. These practical factors will shape how the EPIC-WE game jam method is adapted (see Figure 2). Game jams are usually fast-paced and intensive, so we need to make sure participants have enough space to engage without feeling overwhelmed.

Game jams can last anywhere from a single day to several weeks. For this collaboration, a minimum of one week is needed to give participants time to reflect on the theme and develop ideas. To help manage attention and energy levels, the jam will be spread across several sessions rather than run continuously.

We'll engage only lightly with the "create" phase. By the end of the "imagine" phase, participants will have had time to explore the theme, reflect on key messages, and shaped how those ideas could be expressed in a playable game prototype. This approach allows for meaningful engagement while keeping the process manageable. Additionally, it is not always practical to have a public demonstration of the games in the form of an expo. However, it should be noted that game jams often are reviewed with small prizes given out to conclude the proceedings.

Phase / Contact Point	Experience / 1	Play / 2	Imagine / 3	Create / 3
Aims	Experience games + GREAT water security activities	Play with game concepts + water security theming	Create prototype of chosen idea for playtest	Refine for submission
Process	Introduce/Evoke, Team-up, Define/Decide	Brainstorm, tinker, conceptualise ideas	Iterate, prototype towards a finalised idea	Use playtesting to refine final design
Outcome	Game ideas + water security theme representation	Written development log that captures ideas and feedback	Playable Prototype, Concept Art	Refined prototype
Transition Tool	Group discussions on ideas, sketches + feedback	Hub Council to feedback on ideas	Playtest Game and describe how it is connected to theme	Submit game and rulesheet, conclude and give prizes

Figure 2. Overview of the adapted EPIC-WE game jam methodology used for the collaboration across three contact points with participants. Due to logistical restrictions of participants, there will be limited engagement with the “create” phase. The experience phase will use playful activities developed in GREAT to expose participants to the theme.

Data Collection

With this collaboration we are interested in collecting data in three areas

Development of ideas and values towards theme: At Each transition stage between game jam phases, we will collect perceptions through development logs and discussions of how the theme is being translated into a game to observe the key messages that students have taken from the initial experience phase. Through interviews, we will examine the final game design with insight and reflection form participants on why they chose to represent the theme of water security in this way.

Participant appraisal of the game jam experience: Participants will be interviewed on their experience of taking part in the game jam to explore challenges and positive experiences from taking part.

Perceived attributes developed by taking part in game a game jam: Due to the collaborative and problem-solving nature of a game jam there is opportunity to develop skills for teamwork, design, and creation. As part of the interview, we will explore the perception of this development. We will also survey students on their perceptions of their teamwork and design skills before and after the game jam.

References:

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